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**Complete genome and QbD-guided reverse vaccinology dataset for
Streptococcus iniae strain SIKU01 causing Streptococcosis in Asian seabass
(*Lates calcarifer*)**

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26 **Abstract**

27 *Streptococcus iniae* is a major fish pathogen responsible for severe losses in global aquaculture.
28 We assembled a complete circular genome for strain SIKU01 (2.09 Mb; 1,855 proteins) and then
29 applied reverse vaccinology to identify conserved and epitope-rich proteins. We then integrated a
30 Quality-by-Design (QbD) framework that links protein properties to manufacturability across
31 recombinant protein and plasmid DNA (pDNA) platforms for the *S. iniae* proteome. Each
32 protein was evaluated in silico for compatibility with anion-exchange (AEX), cation-exchange
33 (CEX), cellulose-based affinity, silica-based affinity, and pDNA purification routes. By linking
34 early-stage genome-scale protein discovery to QbD-based downstream biophysical production
35 constraints, our pipeline in silico identified platform-specific shortlists of cost-effective
36 candidates: 98 AEX, 20 CEX, 100 cellulose, 49 silica, and 57–65 pDNA-compatible proteins,
37 recovering known protective immunogens (e.g., enolase, GAPDH). All raw reads, the complete
38 genome assembly, processed annotation tables, and the full analysis code are publicly available
39 as a reusable dataset.

40

41 **Keywords:**

42 Reverse vaccinology, Quality by Design (QbD), *Streptococcus iniae*, aquaculture vaccines,
43 genome-guided vaccine design, manufacturability screening.

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47 **Background & Summary**

48 *Streptococcus iniae* is a major bacterial pathogen in global aquaculture. It was first
49 identified in the 1976 from an Amazon River dolphin (*Inia geoffrensis*) [1]. Annual losses from
50 *S. iniae* are estimated to exceed USD 100 million worldwide [2]. Outbreak mortality ranges from
51 30-80% in aquaculture ponds [3], with cumulative mortality reaching 70% over 3 months in
52 some species [4]. *S. iniae* has been identified in over 27 fish species [5] and detected on all
53 continents [6,7]. Infections are particularly severe in intensive aquaculture systems, where high
54 stocking densities and environmental stress promote rapid disease transmission [3], affecting
55 economically important species including Asian seabass (*Lates calcarifer*), Nile tilapia
56 (*Oreochromis* spp.), and catfish (*Siluriformes* spp.) [8,9]. *S. iniae* is also zoonotic; sporadic
57 human infections, while rare, have been reported in individuals handling infected fish [10].

58 Conventional control for *S. iniae* relies on broad-spectrum antibiotics [11,12] and on
59 prophylactic vaccines based on whole cells or polysaccharides, which provide only short-term
60 protection in experimental trials [13–15]. In practice, these vaccines often lose efficacy within 4–
61 6 months and are prone to long-term failure due to antigenic variation [16]. Capsular
62 polysaccharides have long been considered key protective antigens in *Streptococcus* spp. [17],
63 but are especially unstable targets because *S. iniae* can rapidly alter its surface structures under
64 immune pressure and the genes responsible for capsule production are not consistently present
65 across all strains of *S. iniae* and belong to the accessory pangenome [16]. As a result, existing
66 whole-cell vaccines often lack durability and fail to provide broad protection against diverse *S.*
67 *iniae* strains in fish farms [17].

68 Developing more effective and affordable vaccines against *S. iniae* therefore requires
69 addressing both biological and manufacturing challenges, particularly antigen cost-efficiency,
70 because aquaculture fish affected by *S. iniae*, such as Nile tilapia and Asian seabass, are
71 considered low- to medium-value fish in commercial aquaculture systems [18]. Current

72 aquaculture biosecurity frameworks emphasize preventive, risk-based management as a more
73 cost-effective strategy than reactive outbreak control in farmed systems [19]. Thus, to replace
74 synthetic antibiotics in farming, vaccines against *S. iniae* must be cost-competitive alternatives to
75 antimicrobial treatments [20]. Accordingly, production constraints require candidate antigens to
76 be sequence-conserved across outbreaks, immunogenic, and compatible with scalable production
77 processes. While most research on *S. iniae* has focused on pathogenesis and the protective
78 efficacy of antigens, relatively little has employed a systematic approach to assess the cost-
79 effectiveness of those experimental vaccine preparations [21]. The Quality by Design (QbD)
80 framework [22], widely used in pharmaceutical manufacturing, provides a systematic approach
81 to address these challenges and link antigen characteristics to downstream manufacturability. Yet
82 its application to the earliest stage of vaccine design: antigen discovery through reverse
83 vaccinology—a foundational step that dictates the success of later, larger-scale upstream
84 cultivation—remains largely underexplored.

85 In this study, we used Illumina sequencing to characterize pathogenic *S. iniae* strains
86 isolated from Asian seabass cultured in aquaculture ponds in Thailand. We applied a combined
87 reverse vaccinology and QbD approach to identify and classify proteins from the *S. iniae*
88 genome. One isolate, designated strain SIKU01, was selected for complete genome assembly and
89 subsequent in silico protein screening. By integrating immunoinformatics with manufacturability
90 criteria, we generated platform-specific shortlists of epitope-rich protein candidates relevant to
91 low-cost vaccine development. This “omics-to-manufacturing” pipeline provides a practical,
92 economically scalable framework for selecting more cost-effective antigens for disease control
93 against *S. iniae* and other vital pathogens in aquaculture.

94 **Technical Validation**

95 **Genome Assembly and Annotation**

96 **Genome Assembly and Functional Annotation of *Streptococcus iniae* SIKU01**

97 We assembled a complete genome of *S. iniae* strain SIKU01 (Asian seabass/Thailand) as
98 a single circular chromosome (2.09 Mb, 37% GC) with no plasmids detected (**Fig. 1a–b**;
99 **Supplementary Fig. 1**). Whole-genome comparisons with reference strains QMA0248 (Asian
100 seabass/Australia) [23], 89353 (Nile tilapia/Taiwan) [24], SF1 (flounder/China) [25], and
101 LSSM211007Si (spotbanded scat/China) confirmed strong macrosyntenic conservation (**Fig. 1c–**
102 **d**; **Supplementary Table 1**). We also analyzed synteny relative to isolate QMA0141 (Amazon
103 river dolphin/USA) from 1976 [1] (**Supplementary Fig. 2**).

104 Annotation of strain SIKU01 identified 2,004 genes, including 1,855 protein-coding
105 sequences and 77 RNAs (**Supplementary Table 2**). Functional classification with InterProScan
106 [26], KEGG Mapper [27], and Gene Ontology (GO) [28] (**Supplementary Tables 3–15**)
107 revealed a broad repertoire of metabolic enzymes, transporters, DNA-repair proteins, and cell-
108 surface factors, along with subsets of stress-response proteins, toxins, and antimicrobial
109 resistance genes (**Fig. 1e**). This comprehensive genome annotation provided the foundation for
110 proteome-wide reverse vaccinology and subsequent Quality-by-Design (QbD) manufacturability
111 screening of proteins (see **Methods** and **Supplementary Information; Supplementary Tables**
112 **6–9**).

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114 **Figure 1. Complete genome assembly and functional annotation of *Streptococcus iniae***115 **strain SIKU01. (a)** Genome assembly and reference-guided workflow from raw reads to a116 validated circular chromosome. **(b)** Assembly and annotation statistics, including genome size,117 GC content, gene counts, and RNA features. **(c)** Comparative macro-synteny of strain SIKU01118 against public *S. iniae* reference strains, showing conserved genomic architecture. **(d)** Metadata

119 of strain SIKU01 and related isolates, including collection date, country, and host species, used

120 in hybrid reference-guided assembly. **(e)** Functional annotation of the strain SIKU01 proteome,

121 including KEGG Mapper categories, Gene Ontology (GO) subcellular localization, and

122 InterProScan domain assignments.

123 **Reverse Vaccinology**124 ***Reverse Vaccinology and Mapping of Antigenic Epitopes***125 Using the annotated strain SIKU01 proteome (N = 1,855 proteins, **Supplementary Table**126 **2**), we applied reverse vaccinology [29–31] to identify proteins with extracellular or surface

127 localization signals and to detect B- and T-cell epitopes by mapping DIAMOND BLASTP [32]

128 hits to immunogenic epitopes from the Immune Epitope Database (IEDB) [33] (**Supplementary**

129 **Table 16–18**). Epitope matches were retained at $E \leq 1 \times 10^{-3}$ (range 10^{-3} to 10^{-16}).
130 This yielded 17 epitope-positive proteins, including classical streptococcal
131 targets previously validated in experimental studies [34–38]. **Table 1** lists these
132 epitope-containing proteins.

133 We then evaluated gene-carriage of epitope-containing proteins across a comprehensive
134 dataset of 90 representative *S. iniae* genomes obtained from NCBI Genomes (**Supplementary**
135 **Table 19; Supplementary Fig. 3**). Enolase, GAPDH, and the 60 kDa chaperonin GroEL were
136 highly conserved across nearly all genomes, whereas other epitope-containing proteins exhibited
137 heterogeneous amino acid conservation patterns, including variable gene carriage
138 (presence/absence) across *S. iniae* strains. All annotated epitope-containing proteins were
139 subsequently carried forward, along with the full SIKU01 proteome, into the QbD
140 manufacturability funnel (**Fig. 2**).

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154 **Table 1. Predicted antigenic epitopes from *S. iniae* strain SIKU01.** Seventeen proteins were
155 identified by DIAMOND searches against the IEDB database ($E \leq 1 \times 10^{-3}$) and are
156 shown with their locus tags in SIKU01, UniProtKB gene name annotations,
157 and matched amino acid epitope sequences with cross-homology to the IEDB
158 database.

Locus tag	Subject ID (gene name in UniProtKB)	Epitope sequence (amino acid)
SIKU01_001181	Enolase	RAAADYLEVPLYNYLG
SIKU01_001378	Metal binding protein of ABC transporter (lipoprotein)	EINTEEEGTPDQISSLIEK
SIKU01_001395	Cell envelope proteinase A	LYIKAIEDAVALGADAINLS
SIKU01_001681	Pneumococcal histidine triad protein D	YVTSHGDHYHYNGKVPYDA
SIKU01_001709	Immunogenic secreted protein	DASGTGKRRAEVMEKLDQWIDRHGGTP
SIKU01_001765	Glyceraldehyde 3 phosphate dehydrogenase	MVVKVGINGFGRIGRLAFRRIQ
SIKU01_001769	Surface exclusion protein	VMLTAVGLTGFKLKKDIK
SIKU01_001890	M protein	QLPSTGDSYNPFFTASAMAI
SIKU01_001902	GroEL	LPTLVLNKIRGTFNVVAVKAPGFGDRRKAM
SIKU01_001991	Inosine 5' monophosphate dehydrogenase [<i>Streptococcus agalactiae</i>]	VVKVGIGPGSIC
SIKU01_001995	Conserved hypothetical protein	AQNLRNILHGSDSIFYTFTS
SIKU01_000047	Amidase	EEKQAANQEAINVA
SIKU01_000165	DNA directed RNA polymerase subunit beta' [<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>]	IDNGRRGRPITGP
SIKU01_000216	Pneumococcal histidine triad protein D	YVTSHGDHFHFYNGKVPYDA
SIKU01_000259	YSIRK signal domain/LPXTG anchor domain surface protein	GVNQFIPFELFGGDGMLTRL
SIKU01_000404	Trigger factor	ELDDELAKDIDEEV
SIKU01_000973	Hypothetical protein SPy1154	DSVLEAQMASQLPVIGGIA

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160 QbD Assessment

161 *Critical Quality Attributes (CQAs) and Critical Process Parameters (CPPs) in the QbD*

162 *Framework*

163 In QbD, CQAs describe the antigen or plasmid properties that determine safety, efficacy,
164 and manufacturability. CPPs define the thresholds and decision rules applied to those attributes
165 to ensure cost-efficient purification across common downstream routes [22]. These include
166 pDNA in two target hosts (zebrafish and Nile tilapia) [39] and recombinant proteins expressed in
167 *E. coli* as bioreactors [40,41], where affinity-purified proteins are modified with silica-binding

168 peptides (SBPs) enabling silica affinity purification [42,43] or cellulose-binding modules
169 (CBMs) enabling cellulose affinity purification [44], whereas unmodified proteins are recovered
170 by ion-exchange chromatography based on their native charge [45].

171 ***Definition of Design Spaces (DS)***

172 We integrated the immunoinformatic dataset into a QbD framework that links
173 immunological relevance with manufacturability (**Table 1**). For *S. iniae* SIKU01 protein
174 candidates selection, the CQAs included predicted expression and annotation features [the
175 coding sequence (CDS)] must encode a complete open reading frame (ORF) [46], and the gene
176 must be present in the core pangenome [47–49]), sequence and structural properties (protein
177 length, in amino acids (aa) [50], molecular weight (MW) [50], hydrophobicity (GRAVY index)
178 [51], instability index (II) [52–54], isoelectric point (pI) [55], and net electrostatic charge (z) of
179 the folded protein in aqueous solution at pH 7 [56]), Sequence variability (normalized Shannon
180 entropy, H.norm, from multiple-sequence nucleotide alignments) [57,58], translational potential
181 [codon adaptation index (CAI)] [41,59,60], in *E. coli*, zebrafish and Nile tilapia), gene
182 characteristics [GC3 fraction (0–1)] [61,62], gene length (nt) [50], and Type IIS sites (count)
183 [63,64]), and external evidence [PubMed PMIDs, IEDB (peptide) data] [33]) (**Table 1**). Route-
184 specific descriptors, such as silica-binding peptide length (~20 aa) [42,43] and cellulose-
185 binding module length (\approx 30–200 aa) [44], although not scored, were also included as
186 CQAs.

187 Design spaces:

- 188 ● **M0 (mandatory inclusion)**. At this stage, protein candidates were retained only if the
189 CDS encoded a protein and the ORF was full-length; sequences that failed either
190 requirement were excluded.

- 191 ● **Pre-M1 (mandatory inclusion).** At this stage, protein candidates were retained only if
192 they were present in the core genome fraction of the pangenome. Any sequence failing
193 these requirements was excluded.
- 194 ● **M1 (general filters).** Retain if protein length 100–699 aa; inverted conservation score (1
195 - H.norm) ≥ 0.98 (mandatory); molecular weight (MW) 20–60 kDa (+2, else 0);
196 literature support (+1, none = 0); IEDB (peptide) present (+3, none = 0).
- 197 ● **M1 (protein route).** Host-specific CAI in *E. coli*, CAI_{ec} (+2 top quartile/–2
198 bottom quartile/0 otherwise); hydrophobicity (GRAVY index -0.5 to
199 $+0.5$) +2; instability index (II) ≤ 40 +1.
- 200 ● **M1 (pDNA routes).** Host-specific CAI in zebrafish (CAI_{dr}) or Nile tilapia (CAI_{on}) scored
201 identically (+2 top quartile/–2 bottom quartile/0 otherwise).
- 202 ● **M2 (downstream manufacturability, platform specific).** In the final stage,
203 manufacturability descriptors were applied. For silica affinity, net charge (z) at pH 7 was
204 used: $z \leq -15$ led to exclusion, $-15 < z \leq -5$ scored -1 , $-5 < z \leq +5$
205 scored $+2$, and $z > +5$ scored $+3$ (capped at $+3$). A soft preference of $+1$ was also
206 added for proteins with isoelectric points (pI) between 7 and 9. Silica-binding peptides
207 were constrained to ~ 20 aa to minimize metabolic cost. To ensure cellulose affinity,
208 proteins were required to be < 400 aa to offset the 30–200 aa carbohydrate-binding
209 module fusion and minimize the chimeric expression burden; longer proteins were
210 excluded. For ion-exchange chromatography, AEX required $pI \leq 6.0$; within this
211 constraint, proteins with net charge (z) at pH 7 were scored as 0 to -5
212 ($+1$), -5 to -15 ($+2$), and ≤ -15 ($+3$). CEX required $pI \geq 8.0$; within this

213 constraint, proteins with net charge (z) at pH 7 were scored as 0 to +5
 214 (+1), +5 to +15 (+2), and $\geq +15$ (+3). For pDNA manufacturability, the GC3
 215 fraction [0–1] was assigned a score of +2 for the top quartile, -2 for the bottom quartile,
 216 and 0 for the middle quartiles. Gene length (nt) shorter than the cohort median scored +1,
 217 while longer genes scored 0. Absence of internal Type IIS sites (count = 0) scored +2,
 218 while presence scored 0.

219 **Table 2. QbD Design Space (DS) criteria for protein selection in *S. iniae* reverse**
 220 **vaccinology.** Each CQA–CPP pair was classified based on the evidence origin (data = empirical
 221 or computational results; expert = expert-driven or literature-derived judgement). The staged
 222 approach (**M0–M2**) integrates immunological relevance with manufacturability constraints
 223 across protein and pDNA routes.

Stage	CQA (attribute)	CPP (criterion / inclusion)	Rationale	Source
M0	CDS, ORF, core gene (SIKU01 proteome)	Must encode valid protein CDS; full-length ORF; present in SIKU01	Ensures genuine protein products and gene-carriage across all strains	Data, expert (genome annotation standards) [46, 47, 48]
Pre-M1	Core genome filter	Retain only genes present in the core genome fraction	Prioritizes proteins conserved across multiple isolates	Data, expert (pangenome analysis) [47, 48, 49]
M1 — General	Protein length (aa), Molecular Weight (MW), inverted conservation score (1 - H.norm), literature support (PMID), IEDB (epitope)	100–699 aa; 20–60 kDa (+2); (1 - H.norm) ≥ 0.98 (mandatory); literature +1; IEDB epitope +3	Filters by size, conservation, and prior immunological evidence	Data, literature, expert [33, 50, 57, 58]
M1 — Protein (<i>E. coli</i>)	CAI (in <i>E. coli</i>), hydrophobicity (GRAVY index), instability index (II)	CAI _{ec} (top quartile +2 / bottom -2); GRAVY index -0.5 to +0.5 (+2); instability index (II) ≤ 40 (+1)	Optimizes bacterial expression and solubility	Data, expert (expression system) [40, 41, 51, 52, 58, 59]
M1 — pDNA (Zebrafish/Nile)	Host-specific CAI	CAI _z or CAI _n (top quartile +2 / bottom -2)	Improves in-vivo translation efficiency in <i>D. rerio</i> / <i>O. niloticus</i>	Data, expert (codon optimization) [39, 41, 58, 59]

tilapia)					
M2 — Silica affinity	Net charge (z) at pH 7, SBP length (aa)	$z \leq -15$ exclude; $-5 < z \leq +5$ (+2); $z > +5$ (+3); SBP ≈ 20 aa	Electrostatic adsorption to silanols; minimize fusion burden	Data, expert (process design) [43, 55]; see also [42] for general tag design principles	
M2 — Cellulose affinity	Protein length (aa); CBM length (aa)	Protein length < 400 aa; CBM 30–200 aa (design constraint)	Balances fusion tag length and protein yield: CBMs are large; short proteins offset metabolic/steric cost	Expert (fusion protein practice) [44]; see also [42] for tag-fusion design context	
M2 — Ion-exchange (AEX/CEX)	pI and net charge (z) at pH 7	AEX: pI ≤ 6 and negative net charge (z); CEX: pI ≥ 8 and positive net charge (z)	Binding/selectivity governed by charge at working pH	Data, expert (chromatography parameters) [45]; see also Bio-Rad LIT310 Rev B	
M2 — pDNA manufacturability	GC3 [0-1], gene length (nt), Type IIS (count)	GC3 top quartile +2 / bottom -2; length \leq median +1; Type IIS count = 0 (+2)	Improves <i>in vivo</i> mRNA stability/expression, and cloning efficiency (Golden Gate Assembly)	Data, expert (molecular design) [60, 61, 62, 63, 64]	

224

225 **Figure 2** summarizes the QbD lifecycle, illustrating how successive filtering stages (**M0–M2**)
 226 progressively narrow the candidate space to proteins that are both immunologically relevant and
 227 compatible with multiple expression and purification platforms. Full thresholds and scoring rules
 228 are provided in **Table 2** and **Methods**. Complete proteome-level distributions of CQA attributes
 229 and their pairwise correlations (Spearman’s ρ) are shown in **Supplementary Figs. 4-6**.

230

231 **Figure 2. QbD workflow integrating protein candidate design and manufacturability**
 232 **routes. (a)** The conceptual QbD lifecycle links the Target Product Profile (TPP), in silico protein
 233 scoring, and affinity-tag or plasmid purification strategy through iterative design feedback. **(b)**
 234 The **M2** manufacturability stage defines platform-specific routes—silica affinity and cellulose
 235 affinity, ion-exchange chromatography (AEX/CEX), and pDNA optimization—each of which
 236 translates CQAs into measurable CPPs for scalable vaccine production. **(c)** The workflow
 237 illustrates the progressive narrowing of the design space for protein candidates through
 238 successive QbD stages (**M0** → **Pre-M1** → **M1** → **M2**).

239 **Stepwise QbD reduction of *S. iniae* Proteome ($M0 > Pre-M1 > M1-general$)**

240 At the unfiltered **M0** stage (**Supplementary Table 25**), the proteome (N = 1,855
241 proteins) spanned a wide biophysical space, with hydrophobicity and isoelectric point
242 distributions showing clear bimodality (**Supplementary Fig. 7a**). Applying the **Pre-M1**
243 inclusion gate (core genome carriage) reduced the set to 1,374 proteins (**Supplementary Fig.**
244 **7b**) (**Supplementary Table 26**). **M1-general** filters then retained 1,101 proteins by enforcing
245 protein length 100–699 aa (else excluded), inverted conservation score $((1 - H.\text{norm}) \geq 0.98$,
246 else excluded), molecular weight (MW) 20–60 kDa (+2 points), literature support (+1 point), and
247 IEDB epitope presence (+3 points) (**Supplementary Fig. 7c**) (**Supplementary Table 27**).

248 ***Platform-specific gates (M1)***

249 For the **M1-protein** route in *E. coli* (141 proteins), retained proteins required $\text{CAI}_{\text{ec}} \geq$
250 Q3, moderate hydrophobicity (GRAVY index -0.5 to $+0.5$), and stability
251 (instability index (II) ≤ 40) (**Supplementary Fig. 8a**), detailed in **Supplementary Table**
252 **28**. For the **M1-pDNA** routes, the only gate was host-specific $\text{CAI} \geq \text{Q3}$, yielding
253 zebrafish (212 proteins) and Nile tilapia (207 proteins) (**Supplementary Fig. 8b–**
254 **c**), as detailed in **Supplementary Table 29–30**. GC3 and nucleotide length constraints were not
255 applied until **M2**. In both hosts, density contours showed clustering of retained proteins within
256 narrow ranges of codon usage and sequence length, reflecting platform-specific optimization for
257 translation efficiency and manufacturability.

258 ***Downstream Manufacturability Design Spaces (M2)***

259 To evaluate manufacturability, each downstream platform was subjected to stepwise QbD
260 filtering (**M2** criteria) (**Figure 3, Supplementary Fig. 9**). Mapping proteins into ion-exchange
261 charge space (**Fig. 3a**) showed that most were acidic at pH 7 and thus compatible with AEX,
262 whereas only a minor fraction were sufficiently basic to pass CEX filter. This was reflected in
263 the retained pools (**Fig. 3b**), with 98 proteins retained by AEX and only 20 by CEX. Buffer-

264 specific ranges (**Figs. 3c-f**) confirmed that AEX survivors were stable across nearly all
265 chemistries (82–98 proteins), whereas CEX buffers consistently yielded the same restricted set
266 (~20 proteins). The full protein lists for AEX and CEX are provided in **Supplementary Tables**
267 **31 and 32**.

268 Affinity purification routes imposed distinct orthogonal constraints: Cellulose affinity
269 excluded proteins longer than 400 aa (**Fig. 3g**) to offset the size of the CBM fusion tag (see
270 **Methods** for rationale). Silica affinity (**Fig. 3j**) selected proteins with moderate pI (7–9) and net
271 positive charge, favoring electrostatic compatibility with silanol-rich matrices (see **Methods**).
272 These filters reduced the pools to 100 cellulose-compatible and 49 silica-compatible proteins, as
273 detailed in **Supplementary Tables 33 and 34**.

274 For pDNA platforms, CQAs filters were applied separately for each host. In *O. niloticus*
275 (**Figs. 3h-i**), genes and their products were first assessed for CAI \geq Q3
276 (~ 0.60), ensuring codon usage was well adapted to the host translation
277 machinery; this retained 188 sequences. Applying GC3 \geq Q3 (~ 0.32) halved
278 the pool to 95, as high G/C content at the third codon position improves
279 mRNA stability and reduces metabolic stress. A further protein length cutoff
280 ($\leq 2,200$ nt) yielded 57 proteins, favoring shorter constructs with reduced
281 transcriptional burden. Finally, genes containing internal Type IIS restriction
282 sites (e.g., *Bsa* I, *Sap* I) were excluded because these enzymes cut outside their recognition
283 sites, disrupting modular DNA assembly workflows by preventing a one-step cloning in a
284 Golden Gate Assembly. The final Nile tilapia pDNA pool remained at 57 proteins. In *D. rerio*
285 (**Figs. 3k-l**), the thresholds were slightly higher (CAI \geq Q3 ~ 0.70 , GC3 \geq Q3
286 ~ 0.31). Here, 186 proteins passed the CAI filter, 82 remained after the GC3
287 filter, 66 after the length filter, and 65 after the Type IIS removal filter.

288 Comprehensive candidate sets for both pDNA platforms (zebrafish and Nile
289 tilapia) are available in **Supplementary Tables 35 and 36**.

290 Overall, the QbD funnel produced platform-ready shortlists across all five routes, ranging
291 from 20 (CEX) to 100 (cellulose) candidates for recombinant protein routes and 57–65 for
292 pDNA routes (**Fig. 3b**).

294 **Figure 3. Manufacturability design spaces across purification platforms. (a)** Ion-exchange
295 charge space for protein candidates: pI vs. net charge (z) at pH 7. Shaded bands mark the AEX
296 and CEX inclusion regions; vaccine-referenced antigens are labeled. **(b)** Survivors after **M2**
297 filtering by platform; bars show unique genes per route with counts and percentages. Only
298 proteins that meet the biophysicochemical criteria for their respective purification route are
299 displayed in the color bars. This stage reflects manufacturability constraints and downstream
300 process optimization in the QbD framework. **(c–d)** Buffer operating pH ranges for AEX (c) and
301 CEX (d). Short tick marks indicate the working pH (midpoint of the range). **(e–f)** Protein-route
302 survivors evaluated per buffer at the midpoint. AEX rule: base gate passed, net charge
303 (z) at pH 7 ≤ 0 , and $pI \leq pH_{mid}$. CEX rule: base gate passed, net charge (z) at
304 pH 7 ≥ 0 , and $pI \geq pH_{mid}$. **(g)** Cellulose: protein length distribution for **M2** survivors;
305 dashed line at 400 aa. **(j)** Silica binding peptides may favor proteins with moderate pI (7–9) and
306 positive net charge (z) at pH > 7 . **(h, k)** pDNA (**M2**) scatterplots by host: Nile tilapia **(h)** and
307 zebrafish **(k)**, showing CAI vs. GC3; dashed lines mark the dataset thresholds. **(i, l)** pDNA-route
308 survivors passing each manufacturability gate for Nile tilapia **(i)** and zebrafish **(l)**: CAI \geq
309 threshold, GC3 \geq threshold, length \leq median, and no Type IIS sites (count).

310 **Cross-Validation with Literature**

311 We compiled a literature-based validation dataset of previously tested *S. iniae* vaccine
312 targets across multiple hosts, including channel catfish (*Ictalurus punctatus*) [65], Nile tilapia
313 (*Oreochromis niloticus*) [66], olive flounder (*Paralichthys olivaceus*) [67,68], zebrafish (*Danio*
314 *rerio*) [69], mouse (*Mus musculus*) [70], and turbot fish (*Scophthalmus maximus*) [25]

315 Among the top-ranked proteins consistently found across purification routes, previously
316 studied proteins that demonstrated *in vivo* protection (enolase, GAPDH, and GroEL) were

317 recovered (**Table 3, Supplementary Fig. 10–11**), supporting the predictive accuracy of the QbD
318 approach.

319

320 **Table 3. Compiled vaccine studies against *S. iniae* (and noted cross-challenges).** Each row is
321 a single study arm with study, antigen, accession, RPS (%), pathogen (default *S. iniae* unless
322 specified), antigen dose (μg or CFU), route, type, host, and reference accessions. RPS = relative
323 percent survival post-challenge. Routes: IP = intraperitoneal; IM = intramuscular; Oral + Imm =
324 oral plus immersion; Immersion as listed by authors. Types: D = DNA; P = protein subunit; I =
325 inactivated (e.g., FKC); L = live attenuated; O = other (e.g., combo, nanocarrier); D+O = DNA
326 plus other (e.g., molecular adjuvant). Abbreviations used: FKC = formalin-killed cells; FCA =
327 Freund's complete adjuvant; CNT = carbon nanotube; BNC = bacterial nanocellulose. Cross-
328 protection entries are labeled with the reported pathogen (e.g., *S. agalactiae*, *Edwardsiella*
329 *tarda*). Accessions are GenBank/UniProt (as provided by the original studies).

Study	Antigen	Accession	RPS (%)	Pathogen	Dose	Route	Type	Host	Reference
Giovanni et al., 2025	rC5a	XKE33153.1	30%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	P	Four-finger threadfin	[71]
Giovanni et al., 2025	rC5a + FKC	XKE33153.1	98%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	O (combo)	Four-finger threadfin	[71]
Cao et al., 2023	rSip	OP434413	36%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia	[72]
Cao et al., 2023	rSip	OP434413	32%	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia	[72]
Cao et al., 2023	BNC-rSip	OP434413	68%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia	[72]
Cao et al., 2023	BNC-rSip	OP434413	79%	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia	[72]
Liu et al., 2023	rEno	OP433490	31%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia	[73]
Liu et al., 2023	rEno	OP433490	37%	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	P	Nile tilapia	[73]
Liu et al., 2023	CNT-rEno	OP433490	69%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia	[73]
Liu et al., 2023	CNT-rEno	OP433490	74%	<i>S. agalactiae</i>	–	Immersion	O (nano)	Nile tilapia	[73]
Sheng et al., 2023	rMEPIP (PDHA1)	WP_003099247.1	74%	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 μg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[68]
Sheng et al., 2023	rMEPIG (GAPDH)	ACX85247.1	78%	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 μg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[68]
Sheng et al., 2023	rPDHA1	WP_003099247.1	67%	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 μg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[68]

Sheng et al., 2023	rGAPDH	ACX85247.1	63%	<i>S. iniae</i>	200 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[68]
Liu et al., 2019	pSagH	AAN16978.1	93%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[74]
Liu et al., 2019	pSagH	AAN16978.1	91%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[74]
Liu et al., 2019	pSagH	AAN16978.1	83%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[74]
Liu et al., 2019	pSagH	AAN16978.1	81%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[74]
Sheng et al., 2018	rPDHA1	WP_003099247.1	73%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
Sheng et al., 2018	rPDHA1	WP_003099247.1	75%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
Sheng et al., 2018	rGAPDH	ACX85247.1	64%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
Sheng et al., 2018	rGAPDH	ACX85247.1	63%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
Sheng et al., 2018	rLDH	WP_003099652.1	36%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
Sheng et al., 2018	rLOX	CAA68903.1	36%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
Sheng et al., 2018	rBMP	WP_003099521.1	27%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
Sheng et al., 2018	rOCT	WP_003100983.1	9%	<i>S. iniae</i>	100 µg	IP + FCA	P	Japanese flounder	[75]
E Wang et al. 2016	pcENO + pcIL-8	AGM99057.1, KP701473	80%	<i>S. iniae</i>	25 µg	IM	D + O	Channel catfish	[76]
E Wang et al. 2016	pcENO + pcIL-8	AGM99057.1, KP701473	73%	<i>S. iniae</i>	25 µg	IM	D + O	Channel catfish	[76]
Zhang et al., 2014	rEno	K710_1291	74%	<i>S. iniae</i>	30 µg	IP	P	Turbot	[25]
Zhang et al., 2014	rNeu	K710_1941	77%	<i>S. iniae</i>	30 µg	IP	P	Turbot	[25]
Zhang et al., 2014	rStp	NEAT domain	52%	<i>S. iniae</i>	30 µg	IP	P	Turbot	[25]
Zhang et al., 2014	rHyp1	Not provided	29%	<i>S. iniae</i>	30 µg	IP	P	Turbot	[25]
Zhang et al., 2014	rHem	K710_1282-90	33%	<i>S. iniae</i>	30 µg	IP	P	Turbot	[25]
Sun et al., 2013	pSagE	AF465842.1	95%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[77]
Sun et al., 2013	pSagE	AF465842.1	88%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[77]
Sun et al., 2013	pSagEECR	AF465842.1	68%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[77]
Sun et al., 2012	pSiVa1 (Sia10 + OmpU)	GU458802.1	80–87%	<i>S. iniae</i>	150 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[78]
Sun et al., 2012	pCS10 (Sia10 live carrier)	GU458802.1	81%	<i>S. iniae</i>	~3×10 ⁸ CFU	Oral + Imm	D + O	Japanese flounder	[79]
Sun et al., 2012	pCS10 (Sia10 live carrier)	GU458802.1	69%	<i>E. tarda</i>	~3×10 ⁸ CFU	Oral + Imm	D + O	Japanese flounder	[79]
Sun et al., 2012	pSagF	JQ031813	78%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[80]
Sun et al., 2012	pSagG	JQ031814	65%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[80]

Sun et al., 2012	pSagI	JQ031815	76%	<i>S. iniae</i>	15 µg	IM	D	Japanese flounder	[80]
Sun et al., 2010	pSia10	GU458802.1	74%	<i>S. iniae</i>	40 µg	IM	D	Turbot	[81]
Sun et al., 2010	pSia10	GU458802.1	92%	<i>S. iniae</i>	40 µg	IM	D	Turbot	[81]
Giovanni et al., 2025	FKC (formalin-killed)	–	88%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	I	Four-finger threadfin	[71]
Xiong et al., 2023	FKC (formalin-killed)	–	71%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	I	Golden pompano	[82]
Sheng et al., 2023	FKC (formalin-killed)	–	48%	<i>S. iniae</i>	1×10 ⁸ CFU	IP + FCA	I	Japanese flounder	[68]
Heckman et al., 2022	Live attenuated (E1-r250)	–	95%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[83]
Heckman et al., 2022	Live attenuated (B2-r250)	–	17%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[83]
Heckman et al., 2022	Live attenuated (D2-r250)	–	0%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[83]
Liu et al., 2020	Live attenuated (YM011)	CP032400	93%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[84]
Liu et al., 2020	Live attenuated (YM011)	CP032400	77%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	Oral	L	Nile tilapia	[84]
Liu et al., 2020	Wild type (GX005, challenge)	CP032401	0%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP + Oral	L	Nile tilapia	[84]
Sheng et al., 2018	FKC (formalin-killed)	–	40%	<i>S. iniae</i>	1×10 ⁸ CFU	IP + FCA	I	Japanese flounder	[75]
Wang et al., 2014	Live attenuated (ΔsrtA)	KC352714	96%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[85]
Pridgeon & Klesius, 2011	Live attenuated (ISNO)	GCA_000648555.1	95%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[86]
Pridgeon & Klesius, 2011	Live attenuated (Kent02-N)	–	0%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[86]
Pridgeon & Klesius, 2011	Live attenuated (Uruguay1-N)	–	33%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[86]
Pridgeon & Klesius, 2011	Live attenuated (35Br-N)	–	0%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Nile tilapia	[86]
Buchanan et al., 2005	Live attenuated (ΔPGM)	AY846302	90–100%	<i>S. iniae</i>	–	IP	L	Hybrid striped bass	[87]

330

331 **Structural Modeling of Immunogen Candidates**

332 To further assess their suitability, we modeled two representative proteins known to be
333 immunogenic *in vivo*—GAPDH and enolase—both also well-established in the literature
334 [25,68,73,75,76]. We mapped the predicted epitopes identified in our reverse vaccinology
335 workflow (**Table 1**) to their 3-D structures to determine whether they reside in surface-exposed
336 regions. 3-D Structural predictions generated using AlphaFold2 [88] for *S. iniae* strain SIKU01
337 confirmed highly conserved folds and surface-exposed loops [89]. Several epitope-containing

338 regions identified through reverse vaccinology were surface-accessible (**Fig. 4a–c**, highlighted in
339 yellow), consistent with prior reports [90]. These epitope-containing peptides (**Table 1**) are
340 suitable for direct incorporation into subunit vaccines [67] or for the design of chimeric multi-
341 epitope constructs [68,91]. In summary, both GAPDH and enolase displayed epitope-rich
342 regions spatially separated from catalytic sites and from regions of elevated nucleotide-level
343 sequence variability, reinforcing their functional accessibility and stability as broadly conserved
344 protein candidates.

345

346 **Figure 4. Structural mapping of variability, epitopes, and active sites in two model *S. iniae***

347 **immunogens. (a)** Shannon entropy profiles show that two models and well-known antigens of

348 the scientific literature, GAPDH (gap) and enolase (eno), are largely conserved with limited

349 variable regions. **(b)** GAPDH (336 aa, UniProt Q7BB80) carries a predicted N-terminal epitope

(MVVKVGINGFGRIGRLAFRRIQ) positioned near, but not overlapping with, the active site and adjacent to a region of high nucleotide-level (codon-derived) variability (1–89% variation). (c) Enolase (435 aa, UniProt T1TFA0) contains a predicted epitope (RAAADYLEVPLYNYLG) located opposite the active site and spatially separated from five nucleotide-driven hypervariable surface regions (HR1–HR5), indicating stability and accessibility as a vaccine target. Variability values are based on codon-level polymorphisms within the core-genome alignment and projected onto corresponding amino acid positions in the 3-D models for visualization.

Methods

Bacterial Isolation and Cultivation

Five *Streptococcus iniae* pathogens (designated SIKU01–SIKU05) were isolated from diseased Asian seabass (*Lates calcarifer*) exhibiting clinical signs of streptococcosis. All originated from a single farm in low-salinity culture areas in Chachoengsao Province, Thailand. Pure bacterial cultures were maintained in tryptic soy broth (TSB) containing 25% glycerol at –80°C for long-term storage and for subsequent molecular confirmation and genomic DNA extraction.

Genomic DNA Extraction and gDNA Sequencing

Genomic DNA extraction from *S. iniae* cells involved cultivating bacteria in TSB to the logarithmic phase, followed by cell harvesting and lysis. DNA purification was performed using a column-based method with silica membranes (QIAamp DNA Mini Kit, Qiagen, Germany) according to the manufacturer's protocol with minor modifications for Gram-positive bacteria: The bacterial cell pellets were subjected to enzymatic lysis using hen egg-white lysozyme (20 mg/mL) and overnight incubation at 37°C to digest the peptidoglycan layer, which is particularly thick in Gram-positive bacteria. Following enzymatic treatment, a detergent-based lysis buffer

374 containing proteinase-K was added to complete cell disruption and protein degradation. The
375 quality and quantity of extracted DNA were assessed using a NanoDrop 2000 (Thermo Fisher
376 Scientific, USA) spectrophotometer. High-molecular-weight (HMW) DNA integrity was verified
377 by agarose gel electrophoresis. DNA library preparation and quality control were performed
378 according to standard Illumina sequencing protocols. Sequencing was performed on the Illumina
379 HiSeq 2000 platform (Illumina, USA) sequencer with 151 bp paired-end (PE) chemistry,
380 generating approximately 3 million PE reads per sample.

381 **Genome Assembly and Quality Control**

382 *De Novo Assembly*

383 An initial quality assessment of raw Illumina paired-end (PE) sequencing data was
384 performed using FastQC v0.11.9 (<https://github.com/s-andrews/FastQC>) [92] to evaluate read
385 quality, GC content, and potential adapter contamination. SeqPurge v2019 [93] was used to trim
386 adapter sequences and low-quality bases from the sequencing data using a sliding-window
387 approach, removing bases with quality scores below Q20. *De novo* assembly was performed
388 using Unicycler v0.4.9 [94], which employs SPAdes v3.15.2 [95] as its assembly algorithm. The
389 resulting assembly graphs were visualized using Bandage v0.8.1 [96] to assess connectivity and
390 identify potential misassemblies. Assembly quality metrics were evaluated using QUAST v5.0.2
391 [97].

392 *Reference Guided Assembly*

393 A reference-guided approach was also employed; multiple reference strains (QMA0248,
394 89353, and SF1) were selected from NCBI RefSeq (**Supplementary Table 1**). Reference-guided
395 assembly was performed by mapping trimmed reads to each reference strain genome using
396 Bowtie2 v2.4.4 [98] with the ‘-fast-local’ option. To assess synteny and structural variations

397 across strains, assembly contigs were aligned against all reference genomes using
398 ProgressiveMauve v2.4.0 [99].

399 **Reference-Guided De Novo Assembly**

400 Finally, we applied a hybrid approach to improve genome reconstruction from related *S.*
401 *iniae* strains, combining *de novo* and reference-guided methods [100]. Illumina reads were
402 mapped to an intermediate assembly derived from strain QMA0248, isolated from Asian seabass
403 in Australia [23], using Bowtie2 with the ‘end-to-end’ option and a MAPQ10 quality filter.
404 Variant calling was performed using Pilon v1.23 [101], and SNIPPY v4.6.0
405 (<https://github.com/tseemann/snippy>) [102] was used for remapping the reads. SNIPPY uses
406 BWA-MEM v0.7.17 [103] for read mapping. The CRISPR-Cas locus and other missing
407 insertion-sequence (IS) regions were taken from the *de novo* assemblies. Each assembly was
408 manually inspected using Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV) v2.9.4 [104] to identify and
409 correct potential assembly errors. Assembly quality was further validated by evaluating read
410 mapping statistics, with > 99.7% of reads mapping to the final assemblies, indicating high
411 completeness and accuracy.

412 **Assembly Validation Strategy**

413 *De novo* genome assembly remains a well-known challenge for Illumina-only assemblies
414 due to short read length, missing data, repetitive regions, polymorphisms, and sequencing errors
415 [100]. For genome assembly, we used a hybrid strategy in which we derived the chromosomal
416 structural backbone by mapping reads to the reference genome (strain QMA0248), while *de*
417 *novo* assembly was used to recover CRISPR-Cas and other regions missing from the reference.
418 Additionally, IS sequences were reintegrated into the chromosome at their respective positions
419 after retrieval and comparison with the ISfinder database [105] using advanced *ab initio* methods
420 [106].

421 To ensure the quality and reliability of the *S. iniae* assemblies (SIKU01–SIKU05), we
422 applied multiple validation strategies. We assessed assembly continuity and summary statistics
423 using QUAST v5.3.0, which confirmed high completeness and contiguity across all five
424 genomes, with strain SIKU01 showing characteristics consistent with high-quality bacterial
425 assemblies, including an expected genome size (~2.0 Mb) and a GC content of 36.7%. Structural
426 accuracy was evaluated using multi-genome alignments with ProgressiveMauve, which revealed
427 strong synteny and no major rearrangements relative to closely related *S. iniae* strains. Base-
428 level accuracy was confirmed using SNIPPY for short-read realignment and SNP detection, with
429 manual inspection of selected loci using IGV indicating very few variant calls. To assess
430 mapping quality and potential assembly artifacts, Illumina PE reads were realigned using
431 Bowtie2, and MAPQ0 loci were examined to screen for high-copy-number regions, such as
432 insertion sequences. Overall alignment quality was high, with minimal problematic genomic
433 loci.

434 **Genome Annotation**

435 Genome annotation was first generated for strain SIKU01 with Prokka v1.14.6 [102] and
436 then standardized before GenBank submission using the NCBI Prokaryotic Genome Annotation
437 Pipeline (PGAP) v4.13 [46]. The assembled chromosome FASTA (*CP121692.1.fna*) provided
438 the genomic sequence, which was later joined by locus to form *Sequence_fna*. The
439 corresponding GenBank feature file (*CP121692.1.gb*) was parsed with a custom BioPython
440 script (*S00_gbk_to_table.py*) to produce a flat table (**Supplementary Table 2**) containing one
441 row per gene or CDS feature with coordinates and strand plus the following qualifiers:
442 *anticodon*, *bound_moiety*, *codon_start*, *db_xref*, *EC_number*, *gene*, *gene_synonym*, *inference*,
443 *locus_tag*, *mol_type*, *ncRNA_class*, *note*, *organism*, *product*, *protein_id*, *regulatory_class*,
444 *rpt_family*, *rpt_type*, *rpt_unit_range*, *rpt_unit_seq*, *strain*, *translation*, *transl_table*. For

445 convenience, we retained the core fields *Locus_tag*, *Locus*, *Start*, *End*, *Strand*, *Gene*,
446 *Gene_synonym*, *Product*, *EC_number*, *Codon_start*, *Transl_table*, *Translation*, *Inference*, *Note*,
447 *Protein_id*, and *CDSno*. We generated a simple coordinate index (**Supplementary Table 2b**)
448 containing *Start*, *End*, *Strand*, and *Locus*. We obtained amino acid sequences for similarity
449 searches and domain annotation from the predicted proteome (*Proteome_SIKU01.faa*).

450 ***Functional Annotations and Epitope Detection***

451 For homology transfer, the proteome of strain SIKU01 was aligned against a UniProtKB
452 reference proteome (*UniProtKB_S_iniae_SF1.fasta*) using DIAMOND BLASTP
453 (*identity_threshold* = 90%, *evaluate_threshold* = 1e-10) [32]
454 (*S01_UniProtKB_Mapping_DIAMOND_SIKU01.py*). Hits were captured in **Supplementary**
455 **Table 11** with *query_id*, *subject_id*, *pct_identity*, *aln_length*, *mismatches*, *gap_openings*,
456 *query_start*, *query_end*, *subject_start*, *subject_end*, *evaluate*, *bit_score*; we parsed *subject_id* to
457 recover *Entry_name* for downstream joins to UniProtKB. We obtained functional domain and
458 Gene Ontology (GO) evidence by running InterProScan v5.48-83.0 [26] on
459 *Proteome_SIKU01.faa*, which generated a General Feature File (.gff3) of annotations that we
460 parsed into **Supplementary Table 3** with *Locus* (renamed *Locus_tag*), *Sequence_MD5_digest*,
461 *Sequence_length*, *Analysis*
462 (Pfam/TIGRFAM/SMART/SUPERFAMILY/Gene3D/CDD/PANTHER/ProSite/TMHMM/Ham
463 ap/FunFam), *Signature_accession*, *Signature_description*, *Start_location*, *Stop_location*, *Score*,
464 *Status*, *Date*, *InterPro_annotations_accession* (IPR), *InterPro_annotations_description*,
465 *GO_annotations*. We integrated curated protein-level annotations from a UniProtKB TSV export
466 (**Supplementary Table 10**) including *Entry/Entry Name* (*Entry_name*), *Protein names*, *Gene*
467 *Names*, *Gene Names (primary)*, *Function [CC]*, *Catalytic activity*, *Cofactor*, *Activity regulation*,
468 *EC number*, *Pathway*, *Kinetics*, *pH dependence*, *Site*, *Redox potential*, *Rhea ID*, *Temperature*

469 *dependence, PubMed ID, Keywords/Keyword ID, Protein families, Gene Ontology (GO) and*
470 *sub-ontologies with GO IDs, Subcellular location [CC], Signal peptide, Transmembrane,*
471 *Topological domain, Coiled coil, Helix, Beta strand, Turn, Motif, Domain [CC]/Domain [FT],*
472 *Region, Repeat, Zinc finger, Disulfide bond, Modified residue, Lipidation, Propeptide, Initiator*
473 *methionine, Caution, Comments, Annotation, Features. We mapped to SIKU01 via UniProt*
474 *Entry_name derived from the best-scoring DIAMOND match for each SIKU01 protein, after*
475 *enforcing a one-to-one mapping between the UniProtKB SF1 reference proteome and strain*
476 *SIKU01 (Supplementary Table 11).*

477 Pathway and hierarchy assignments used KEGG Mapper/BRITE [27], and GO terms
478 followed the Gene Ontology framework [28,107] (Supplementary Table 3–9). Transmembrane
479 helices and bacterial Gram-positive N-terminal signal peptides were predicted with TMHMM
480 v2.0 [108] and SignalP v5.0 [109], respectively. Additional family/domain calls from InterPro's
481 member databases [26] (including InterPro families [110], Pfam [111], SMART [112],
482 TIGRFAMs [113], and SUPERFAMILY [114]) were considered where present.

483 ***Protein-level Biophysical Descriptors Calculation***

484 Protein-level biophysical descriptors were computed from amino acid sequences using
485 the Peptides R package [115] (S02_Peptides_Physicochemical_Properties_SIKU01.R) and
486 additionally calculated from translated protein sequences (.faa) in *Proteome_SIKU01.faa* using
487 the SeqinR R package [116]. For each protein, we calculated the theoretical isoelectric point (pI),
488 molecular weight (MW), net charge (z) at pH 6.8, 7.0, and 7.4, hydrophobicity (GRAVY index),
489 instability index (II), sequence length (aa), and the aliphatic index for exploratory correlation
490 analyses. We computed summary statistics (mean, median, and standard deviation) for each
491 descriptor and added them directly onto faceted distribution plots as text annotations for

492 reporting. These descriptors fed **Matrix-1** filters (solubility, stability, manufacturability biases)
493 and **Matrix-2** platform compatibility rules. Physicochemical descriptors computed from the
494 amino acid sequences were appended as *Charge_pH_6_8*, *Charge_pH_7*, *Charge_pH_7_4*,
495 *aliphatic_Index*, *hydrophobicity*, *instability_index*, *binding_potential*, *length_AA*, *mw*, *pI* to a
496 subset UniProtKB TSV data (**Supplementary Table 11**), summarizing SIKU01
497 physicochemical properties of individual proteins (**Supplementary Table 15**).

498 An epitope evidence layer (**Supplementary Tables 16–17**) was merged with *Locus_tag*;
499 this table includes *evaluate_epitope_prediction*, *pct_identity_epitope_prediction*, and
500 *bit_score_epitope_prediction* for matches to curated *Streptococcus* spp. epitopes retrieved from
501 IEDB and aligned to the *S. iniae* SIKU01 proteome with DIAMOND BLASTP
502 (S03_IEDB_Epitope_Mapping_DIAMOND_SIKU01.py). Epitope hits were retained at $E \leq 1$
503 $\times 10^{-3}$ (observed range 10^{-3} to 10^{-16}) (**Supplementary Table 18**).

504 ***PubMed Literature Search***

505 PubMed evidence and PMID metadata were retrieved using the custom script
506 (S04_PubMed_Metadata_Retrieval_SIKU01.R), with proteins that had prior experimental
507 mentions, particularly as vaccine candidates or virulence factors, receiving graduated positive
508 scores based on the strength of the evidence (**Supplementary Table 14**).

509 ***Annotation Merging and Biophysical Analysis***

510 All previous layers were merged using a custom script
511 (S05_Merge_Annotations_SIKU01.R) and manual curation, cross-checking UniProtKB
512 keywords/feature texts with InterPro domain calls, KEGG/GO assignments, and the primary
513 PGAP/Prokka annotations to produce the combined initial table (**M0**) used in downstream QbD

514 scoring (**Supplementary Table 25**). Finally, plots and distributions were generated using a
515 custom script (S06_Biophysical_Analysis_SIKU01.R).

516 ***Pangenomics and Sequence Variability Analysis***

517 Ninety representative *Streptococcus iniae* genomes were obtained from NCBI Genomes
518 (**Supplementary Table 19**) and were annotated using Prokka [102] to homogenize coding
519 sequence (CDS) annotations prior to graph-based pan-genome clustering with Panaroo [48],
520 which implements an improved orthology graph algorithm originally inspired by Roary [47].
521 Clustering was performed at a high amino acid identity threshold ($\geq 85\%$)
522 and a core gene inclusion cutoff of 95%, with paralogues excluded. This
523 graph-based ortholog clustering step produced **Supplementary Tables 20**,
524 including a gene presence/absence (P/A) matrix (.Rtab) (*S20_gene_presence_absence.Rtab*) and
525 a summary that links each gene sequence and its annotation (*S20_gene_data.csv*), used to parse
526 the final pangenome graph (*final_graph.gml*).

527 To annotate each genome with consistent pan-genome metadata, we used a custom script
528 (S07_Generate_pangenome_IDs_Panaroo.py) adapted from Panaroo's post_run_gff_output.py
529 utility (available at
530 https://github.com/gtonkinhill/panaroo/blob/master/panaroo/post_run_gff_output.py). This
531 script integrated Panaroo's graph and table outputs to reconstruct strain-
532 specific GFF3 annotation files containing standardized pangenome
533 attributes. The Rtab file served as the quantitative input to determine gene
534 carriage frequency across strains and to assign each orthogroup to a
535 pangenome class (core, soft-core, shell, or cloud) based on its prevalence
536 thresholds ($\geq 99\%$, 95–98%, 15–94%, and $< 15\%$, respectively). These

537 classifications were used to generate augmented presence/absence (P/A)
538 tables (*S20_gene_presence_absence_pangenomeid.csv*,
539 *S20_gene_presence_absence_roary_pangenomeid.csv*, and
540 *S20_gene_presence_absence_Rtab_pangenomeid.csv*) and an index table
541 (*S20_pangenome_ids.csv*) linking each Panaroo cluster ID to its class, representative gene, and
542 genome distribution.

543 To assign SIKU01-specific locus tags to orthogroups, we extracted *S. iniae* SIKU01
544 clusters from the Panaroo tables using a custom script (*S08_extract_SIKU01_PIDs.sh*). This
545 script filtered the pangenome Rtab file to produce **Supplementary Table 21**
546 (*S21_PID_SIKU01.csv*).

547 We enriched this dataset with GFF-derived attributes using another custom script
548 (*S09_pid_locus_extractor.sh*), which cross-referenced *pangenome_id* entries against the
549 Panaroo-generated GFF file (*SIKU01_panaroo.gff*) to create a unified annotation table
550 (*S21_PID_SIKU01_with_attrs.tsv*). Although biased toward the SIKU01 reference strain, this
551 approach provided a one-to-one mapping between pangenome clusters and genome-specific
552 locus tags, enabling precise tracking of orthogroups during downstream conservation analysis.

553 For each genome, we extracted CDS and translated protein sequences from annotated
554 GFF3 files using *gffread* [117]. We concatenated all orthologous sequences into tagged FASTA
555 files (*ALL_CDS.tagged.fa* and *ALL_AA.tagged.fa*) with *SeqKit* [118]. We then processed these
556 combined FASTA files with a custom pipeline (*S10_generate_MSAs_for_conservation.py*),
557 which automatically retrieved sequences by pangenome cluster ID and performed per-cluster
558 multiple sequence alignments (MSAs) with *MAFFT* [119] or *Clustal Omega* [120], depending
559 on cluster size. The resulting nucleotide- and amino acid-level MSAs formed the foundation for
560 subsequent analyses of sequence variability, conservation, and structure-based mapping.

561 We analyzed all MSAs in R using a custom script
562 (S11_Conservation_Shannon_SIKU01.R), which calculated normalized Shannon entropy
563 (H.norm) at both codon and amino acid levels via the Bio3D package [58]. For each
564 orthogroup, H.norm quantified sequence variability on a continuous scale
565 from 0 (fully conserved) to 1 (maximally variable). Proteins with median
566 inverted conservation scores ($1 - H.\text{norm}$) ≥ 0.98 were classified as highly
567 conserved, whereas those with scores below 0.90 were excluded as
568 excessively variable.

569 These metrics, together with gene-carriage data from Panaroo, defined the gene-carriage
570 and sequence-variability design space of the QbD framework (**Pre-M1** and **M1** matrices).
571 Collectively, these datasets laid the foundation for the downstream biophysical and
572 immunological filtering steps described in the following Quality-by-Design methods section.

573 ***Protein Structure Prediction and Visualization***

574 Three-dimensional structures of model *S. iniae* antigens (GAPDH, enolase, GroEL,
575 Sortase A) were based on their predicted structures in AlphaFold2 [88] and cross-validated
576 against available homologous templates in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) [121]. Predicted PDB
577 files (AF_model_ranked_0.pdb) were examined in UCSF ChimeraX v1.6 [122] for fold
578 integrity, residue geometry, and solvent accessibility.

579 To quantify site-specific structural conservation, we implemented a per-residue identity
580 analysis (S12_Conservation_Plot_ChimeraX.py) that scanned each MAFFT-aligned FASTA
581 (*_aln.faa). For every alignment, the script compared all sequences to the reference (first entry)
582 and recorded, for each residue position, the number and percentage of identical residues across
583 all genomes, producing *_identity.csv files. These per-site identity profiles were mapped onto

584 AlphaFold2 models in ChimeraX using custom color scripts to generate gradient-based
585 visualizations, with blue indicating highly conserved residues and red denoting variable
586 positions. This approach provided a direct link between MSA entropy (1 - H.norm) values and 3-
587 D spatial conservation, highlighting structurally stable and immunologically relevant regions.

588 Epitope localization was subsequently performed using a custom script
589 (S13_Epitope_Locator_ChimeraX_PDB.py), which scanned PDB chains for exact matches to
590 epitope peptide sequences identified by IEDB mapping. For each hit, the script reported the
591 model ID, chain ID, and PDB residue range corresponding to the matched peptide, enabling
592 precise overlay of B- and T-cell epitopes onto predicted protein structures.

593 Surface visualization and electrostatic potential mapping were carried out in ChimeraX
594 using the “surface color” and “cartoon” representations to assess accessibility and topological
595 context. Together, these in silico steps provided a reproducible pipeline linking sequence-level
596 conservation, structural integrity, and epitope exposure within the QbD framework.

597 ***Codon Adaptation Index (CAI) and Expression Compatibility***

598 Codon usage frequencies for target organisms were obtained from the Kazusa Codon
599 Usage Database [60] and used to calculate Codon Adaptation Index (CAI) values. The CAI
600 quantifies the degree of preference for synonymous codons in a given organism, where values
601 range from 0 (least preferred) to 1 (most preferred). For each amino acid family, the relative
602 adaptiveness of codon i was calculated as $w_i = f_i / f_{max}$, where f_i represents the frequency per
603 thousand of codon i for its amino acid and f_{max} represents the frequency per thousand of the
604 most frequently used codons for that amino acid. For example, proline codons in *Oreochromis*
605 *niloticus* were calculated as follows: CCG had $w_i = 7.39 / 16.53 = 0.447$, CCA
606 had $w_i = 14.59 / 16.53 = 0.883$, CCT had $w_i = 16.53 / 16.53 = 1.000$

607 (optimal), and CCC had $w_i = 14.91 / 16.53 = 0.902$. The value 16.53
608 represents the highest frequency among all proline codons, making CCT the
609 optimal reference codon. Next, for complete gene sequences, CAI was
610 computed as the geometric mean of relative adaptiveness values using the
611 formula $CAI = (\prod_{k=1}^L w_k)^{1/L}$, where the product encompasses all L sense
612 codons in the gene sequence and L represents the total number of sense
613 codons excluding stop codons. Stop codons (TAA, TAG, TGA) and the single
614 methionine codon (ATG) were excluded from CAI calculations as they lack
615 synonymous alternatives for optimization. CAI values were implemented by
616 first parsing codon frequency tables, then identifying the optimal codon for
617 each amino acid, calculating relative adaptiveness for all 61 sense codons,
618 and finally computing the geometric mean of constituent codon values for
619 gene sequences.

620 **Quality-by-Design (QbD)**

621 To implement QbD within the reverse vaccinology framework, we defined quantitative scoring
622 criteria (S14_QbD_Ranking_SIKU01.R) to assign proteins to platform-specific shortlists.

623 ***QbD Design Space for Gene Carriage (Matrix Pre-M1)***

624 This Critical Quality Attribute (CQA) is based on the pangenome presence/absence
625 matrix, in which, in *S. iniae*, the core genome (present in $\geq 99\%$ of strains) was
626 retained, whereas soft-core genome (95–98%), shell (15–94%) and cloud (<
627 15%) genes were excluded from further evaluation. Depending on the Panaroo
628 parameterization and filtering, this yielded 1,374–1,538 core genes, which formed the basis for

629 subsequent analyses of sequence variability and QbD scoring, given their broad distribution and
630 genetic stability.

631 ***QbD Design Space for Amino Acid and Nucleotide Variability (Matrix 1)***

632 Normalized Shannon entropy () defined the design space for protein and nucleotide
633 variability and was quantified from per-cluster MSAs (see above). Per-site values from
634 sequence alignments ranged from 0 (fully conserved) to 1 (maximally
635 variable). For gene-level prioritization, entropy values were summarized per
636 alignment using the mean and median of H.norm. An inverted conservation
637 score ($1 - H.\text{norm}$) was then used for downstream filtering so that higher
638 values indicated greater conservation. Genes with median inverted
639 conservation scores ≥ 0.98 were prioritized as structurally and functionally
640 stable. Residues with low entropy and high surface exposure, as confirmed
641 by ChimeraX 3-D mapping, defined the structural conservation-driven QbD
642 design space.

643 ***QbD Design Space for General Physicochemical and Expression Characteristics (Matrix 1)***

644 General **Matrix-1** CQAs were chosen to favour proteins that are practical to express,
645 purify, and formulate. Protein length and molecular weight were constrained to select proteins
646 large enough to carry multiple epitopes but not so large as to be difficult to fold or manufacture
647 at scale. pI and hydrophobicity (GRAVY index) were used to prioritize soluble proteins
648 compatible with standard aqueous buffers and multiple purification chemistries, while the
649 instability index (II) was used to down-weight intrinsically unstable proteins. Finally, literature
650 support (PubMed evidence) allowed us to up-rank proteins with prior experimental validation as

651 virulence factors or vaccine targets. The exact thresholds and scoring rules for these CQAs are
652 summarized in **Table 2 (Matrix 1)**.

653 ***QbD Design Space for Immunogenicity (Matrix 1)***

654 Epitope prediction analysis identifies known sequences that stimulate human and mouse
655 T and B lymphocytes using the IEDB database. Proteins predicted to contain both B- and T-cell
656 epitopes receive the highest immunological relevance score, whereas proteins lacking predicted
657 epitopes are down-weighted during scoring.

658 ***QbD Design Space for Host-specific Expression (Matrix 1 – CAI)***

659 *In-vitro* expression efficiency prediction uses the Codon Adaptation Index (CAI) to
660 assess translational compatibility with *E. coli* systems, following the principle of optimal codon
661 usage to maximize protein expression. Top-quartile CAI values receive positive weighting, while
662 bottom-quartile scores may indicate potentially lower in vivo expression.

663 ***QbD Design Space for Matrix 2 – Secondary Selection***

664 **Overview In Matrix 2**, candidate proteins from **Matrix 1** were screened multiple times for
665 compatibility with specific downstream purification modalities by aligning their intrinsic
666 molecular descriptors with platform-specific CPPs. Five distinct sets of design spaces were
667 evaluated: silica affinity, cellulose affinity, ion-exchange chromatography (IEX; anion exchange
668 and cation exchange), and pDNA expression. This pre-downstream design space cross-
669 references in silico CQAs with platform-specific CPPs to ensure process–protein compatibility
670 before physical development, thereby maximizing cost-efficiency post-biomanufacturing.

671 **Silica Affinity Purification**, silica-based purification technologies offer ubiquity, low cost, and
672 adaptability across laboratory and industrial bioprocessing applications. Critical Material

673 Attributes (CMAs) include silanol density, surface topology, and functionalization chemistry,
674 while key CPPs encompass pH, ionic strength, and buffer composition. Affinity tags with high
675 silica specificity, including Si-tag, SB7, Car9, R5, and the synthetic octapeptide (RH)₄,
676 composed of four repeating Arginine-Histidine units, interact with silanol-rich
677 matrices via electrostatic and hydrogen-bonding interactions. Proteins presenting net
678 positive charge (*z*) at pH 7.4 demonstrate enhanced adsorption due to electrostatic
679 attraction to partially deprotonated silanol groups ($\equiv\text{Si-OH} \rightarrow \equiv\text{Si-O}^-$). QbD selection
680 criteria required *pI* > 4 and a surface-exposed cationic patch at loading pH (offered by the
681 fusion of a silica binding peptide short tag). Elution is achieved by increasing pH from 7.4 to 8.5,
682 expanding silanol deprotonation and reducing hydrogen-bond donor capacity. Short tag lengths
683 (~7–20 aa) were favored to avoid steric hindrance and folding interference.

684 **Cellulose Affinity Purification**, cellulose-based purification utilizes cellulose-binding
685 modules (CBMs) such as CBM3, CBM9, or CelD, which recognize repeating β -(1→4)-D-
686 glucopyranose units through hydrogen bonding with hydroxyl groups and hydrophobic
687 stacking with planar glucan rings. Key CPPs include buffer pH (6.0–8.5), salt concentration,
688 cellulose type, and contact time. Since binding is mediated by the CBM domain rather than
689 protein charge properties, no *pI* requirement was applied. However, CBMs add
690 substantial polypeptide segments (30–200 aa), necessitating length
691 constraints. We retained proteins \leq 400 aa to ensure that total fusion
692 constructs remained \leq 430–630 aa. This limit reduces metabolic burden,
693 misfolding risk, and aggregation while maintaining tag accessibility.

694 **Ion-exchange chromatography (IEX)**, IEX utilizes the net charge of a protein to separate it
695 from other proteins. Depending on the resin chemistry and the protein charge, either anion-
696 exchange or cation-exchange chromatography is used. Anion exchange chromatography was
697 modeled on quaternary amine functional groups [e.g., $-N^+(CH_3)_3$], which bind negatively
698 charged proteins through electrostatic interactions with deprotonated carboxyl groups. The QbD
699 filter retained proteins with $pI \leq 6.5$ and net charge $z \leq -1$ at pH 7.4. Cation
700 exchange chromatography employed sulfonate ligands ($-SO_3^-$) that bind
701 protonated amines from Lys, Arg, and His side chains. Selection criteria
702 favored proteins with $pI \geq 8.0$ and net charge $z \geq +1$ at pH 7.4, ensuring
703 positive charge under working conditions for effective resin binding.

704 **Plasmid DNA Expression** (pDNA) was treated as a distinct design space, with optimization of
705 expressed proteins for high-yield, high-fidelity eukaryotic expression in pDNA. Sequence-level
706 CQAs included GC3 enrichment to improve *in vivo* mRNA stability and translation
707 efficiency, ORF length threshold (set at the median coding sequence length
708 of core genes ≈ 2.2 kb), and complete absence of internal Type IIS restriction
709 sites (*Bsa* I, *Bsm* BI, *Eco* 31I) to ensure seamless Golden Gate Assembly cloning compatibility.

710 **Statistical Analysis**

711 All statistical analyses were performed in R version 4.2.0. We calculated Spearman's
712 rank correlation coefficients using the `cor()` function with `method="spearman"`. We assessed
713 statistical significance using the `rcorr()` function from the `Hmisc` package, with significance set at
714 $p < 0.05$. For the exploratory correlation between hydrophobicity and aliphatic index ($\rho = 0.82$, p
715 $< 10^{-15}$), significance was calculated using `cor.test()`. Although we did not apply formal
716 corrections for multiple testing in this exploratory analysis, key correlations (e.g.,
717 hydrophobicity-aliphatic index, $\rho = 0.82$) would remain significant after Bonferroni correction.

718 Kernel density estimation was performed using the density() function with 512
719 interpolation points. Density contours in scatter plots were generated using ggplot2's
720 stat_density_2d() with default bandwidth selection. All histograms used 50 bins for consistency
721 across distributions.

722 Normalized Shannon entropy for sequence variability [57] was calculated for proteins
723 present in at least 95% of genomes as $H = -\sum(\pi_i \times \log_2(\pi_i))$, where π_i is the frequency of an
724 amino acid at each position. Normalized entropy (H.norm) was calculated as $H / \log_2(20)$, to
725 scale values between 0 (fully conserved) and 1 (maximum variation), using the Bio3D package
726 [58]. For downstream prioritization, an inverted conservation score ($1 -$
727 $H.\text{norm}$) was used so that higher values indicated greater sequence
728 conservation. Quartile thresholds for the codon adaptation index (CAI) and
729 GC3 content were calculated using quantile() at 0.25 and 0.75 probabilities.
730 All thresholds were calculated on the **Pre-M1** filtered dataset ($n = 1,374$ proteins) to
731 ensure consistency across platforms.

732 For multimodal distribution detection, hierarchical density-based clustering (HDBSCAN)
733 was applied with minPts=40 using the dbscan package. Statistical summaries (mean, median,
734 standard deviation) were calculated for all biophysical properties, including molecular weight
735 (MW), isoelectric point (pI), hydrophobicity (GRAVY index), and instability index (II). The
736 dataset **M0**, comprising the full SIKU01 proteome ($N = 1,855$ proteins) and the **Pre-M1** filtered
737 subset ($n = 1,374$ proteins), provided adequate statistical power for correlation analyses.

738 **Data Records**

739 All genome assemblies and raw sequencing data generated in this study have been
740 deposited in public repositories. The project has been registered under NCBI BioProject
741 [PRJNA933632](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA933632), with the BioSample accession number [SAMN33244440](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample/SAMN33244440). Raw sequencing reads

742 are hosted in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA): Illumina 151 bp paired-end, 10 FASTQ
743 files, 5 raw sequencing datasets; [SRR23406918](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406918) for strain SIKU01, while other accessions were
744 [SRR23406921](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406921), [SRR23406920](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406920), [SRR23406919](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406919), and [SRR23406922](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR23406922) for strains SIKU02–SIKU05,
745 respectively. The annotated genome for strain SIKU01 has been submitted to NCBI GenBank
746 and is available under [CP121692.1](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/CP121692.1). Due to time constraints, only strain SIKU01 was submitted
747 to NCBI GenBank.

748 **Data Availability**

749 Complete datasets supporting this study are provided as Excel files; other data can be
750 accessed via the Zenodo project repository (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15264953>).

751 ● **Supplementary Data 1:** Genome metadata, proteome annotation, and pre-QbD inputs
752 (Tables S01–S08).

753 ● **Supplementary Data 2:** Stagewise QbD filtering results and manufacturability matrices
754 for all routes (Tables S09–S21).

755 ● **Supplementary Data 3:** Literature validation of vaccine performance in fish models
756 (Tables S22–S23).

757 The Zenodo release also contains processed datasets, including SIKU01 proteome annotations,
758 epitope-positive protein sets, gene-carriage and conservation summaries across the 90-genome *S.*
759 *iniae* dataset, QbD design-space criteria, and route-specific protein candidate lists for AEX,
760 CEX, cellulose affinity, silica affinity, and pDNA production platforms.

761

762 **Code Availability**

763 All computational tools used in this study are publicly available, and all command-line
764 parameters are described in the Methods section. Custom scripts for data processing, proteome
765 annotation, and Quality-by-Design (QbD) manufacturability analysis are provided in the
766 **Supplementary Code** and archived on Zenodo (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15264953>)
767 in the folder Supplementary_Code/.

768 The archive includes scripts for genome annotation parsing, reference mapping,
769 physicochemical profiling, epitope detection, literature evidence retrieval, and annotation
770 integration, including: S00_gbk_to_table.py (GenBank feature table extraction),
771 S01_UniProtKB_Mapping_DIAMOND_SIKU01.py (UniProtKB reference mapping),
772 S02_Peptides_Physicochemical_Properties_SIKU01.R (proteome physicochemical profiling),
773 S03_IEDB_Epitope_Mapping_DIAMOND_SIKU01.py (IEDB epitope detection),
774 S04_PubMed_Metadata_Retrieval_SIKU01.R (PubMed evidence and PMID metadata retrieval),
775 S05_Merge_Annotations_SIKU01.R (annotation merging),
776 S06_Biophysical_Analysis_SIKU01.R (proteome-wide biophysical analysis),
777 S12_Conservation_Plot_ChimeraX.py (mapping sequence conservation onto AlphaFold2 protein
778 structures using ChimeraX),
779 S13_Epitope_Locator_ChimeraX_PDB.py (epitope mapping onto predicted structures), and
780 S14_QbD_Ranking_SIKU01.R (QbD scoring and manufacturability filtering).

781 Scripts supporting pangenome reconstruction and sequence variability analysis include:
782 extra_run_panaroo.sh, extra_concatenate_core_genome.py,
783 S07_Generate_pangenome_IDs_Panaroo.py, S08_extract_SIKU01_PIDs.sh,
784 S09_pid_locus_extractor.sh, S10_generate_MSAs_for_conservation.py, and
785 S11_Conservation_Shannon_SIKU01.R.

787 Usage Notes

788 To reproduce the QbD prioritization, download the Zenodo archive (scripts and processed tables)
789 and run S14_QbD_Ranking_SIKU01.R, which regenerates the final ranked protein table and
790 platform-specific shortlists. Intermediate outputs—including pangenome matrices, epitope
791 mappings, and sequence variability metrics—are provided as Supplementary Tables and within
792 the Zenodo archive.

793

794 Author Contributions Statement

795 Quentin Ludovic Stephane Andres: Conceptualized the study, developed the methodology,
796 extracted DNA, performed bioinformatic analysis, curated data, generated visualizations, wrote
797 the original draft. Prapansak Srisapoom: Collected samples, extracted DNA, and performed
798 DNA sequencing. Kornorn Srikulnath and Worapong Singchat: Collected samples. Prapansak
799 Srisapoom: Collected samples, supervised the project, and managed project administration.

800 Competing Interests

801 The authors declare no competing interests.

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1183 **Other Files**1184 *Supplementary_Information.docx*1185 *Description_of_Additional_Supplementary_Files.docx*